

ORGANIZING PRACTICAL EDUCATION COURSES ON SEWING PROFESSION FOR STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

Hasanova Vasila Ergashevna

Technology science teacher of the 186th general secondary school in the Shaikhontohur district of Tashkent city

Annotation: This article describes the procedure, importance and effectiveness of organizing practical education training sessions on the secrets and profession on sewing for students with disabilities.

Keywords: education, practical training, tailoring profession, disabilities, creative approach, sewing, result.

Introduction: Based on the rich cultural heritage and values of our people, the creation of an excellent system of tailor-pedagogical personnel training based on the achievements of modern sewing technology has become one of the important conditions for the development of education in Uzbekistan. In this case, a system aimed at training personnel who is aspiring to creative activity, capable of mastering new techniques and technologies in the field of tailoring is used. Currently, tailoring production is a very broad industry, in which advanced means of automation and mechanization, computer equipment, scientific and technical achievements are widely used. All this requires tailors to be highly educated, acquire skills and qualifications. The organizers of the sewing club, which conducts educational activities outside the school and classroom, should know how to make products that meet all the requirements, using new modern technologies and using modern equipment and devices in the production of clothes based on an individual order. However, the field of organizing practical training in tailoring for students with disabilities is different from teaching this field to able-bodied students. In this case, the master of production education must be creative, inquisitive, enterprising, and have pedagogical skills.

It is known that the main task of tailoring specialists is to improve the quality of clothing. One of the important advanced directions in the development of tailoring is the introduction of the method of thermofixation, that is, the method of gluing other materials to the details of outerwear. It is important to pay attention to every detail in the organization of practical training in tailoring for students with disabilities. In particular, the introduction of sewing equipment to a hand needle, sewing machine, scissors, iron, sewing machine and sewing equipment is explained based on the possibilities of each student. It is also taught how to use a hand needle for temporary blueing, pleating and embroidering details. In modern conditions, it is demanded that the educational process should be directed to the development, socialization and training of independent, critical and creative thinking abilities. Education that can show these possibilities is called person-oriented education. The use of personalized educational technologies gives a very effective result. Therefore, taking into account the student's thinking and action strategy, it directs the development of his personality, characteristics, and abilities. This means that the educational environment should be adapted to the student's abilities. According to him, the educational environment, pedagogical conditions, education and training process implies the full realization of the student's personal

potential, development of abilities, ensuring that he matures as a person, enriching his thinking and worldview.

In organizing training sessions for students with disabilities on the secrets and profession of tailoring, a unique aspect of person-oriented education is to recognize the learner's personality, to create a comfortable and necessary environment for his comprehensive development. This type of education in the educational process serves to educate students such qualities as independence, creativity, initiative, responsibility, as well as independent, creative and critical thinking skills. In the organization of this type of education, pedagogues are required to approach each student as individually as possible, respect his personality, and show confidence in him. In addition, person-oriented education represents the need to create a favorable pedagogical environment for the participants of the teaching process to learn in mutual cooperation in the form of a pedagogue-student or student-student, group of students, student-student team, to develop as a person. Person-oriented technology is based on the intellectual and emotional-motivational development of students, the formation of knowledge and professional skills, the provision of an approach to the educational process as a value, increasing activity, forming self-awareness and independence.

Conclusion: In short, it is worth noting that, in organizing practical education training sessions on sewing profession for students with disabilities pedagogues need to pay special attention to ensuring that students have the opportunity to use educational information based on their knowledge, skills, qualifications and experience, to interest them, to encourage them to think, to be creative.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdurahmanova, M. T., & Rayimjonova, M. M. (2021). PARALLEL KORPUSLARDA TARJIMA MASALASI. *Global Science and Innovations: Central Asia* (см. в книгах), 2(9), 47-50.
2. ОТАЖОНОВА, М. (2017). ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ МИФОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ СЮЖЕТОВ В УЗБЕКСКИХ ПРОЗАИЧЕСКИХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ. *Научное обозрение Саяно-Алтая*, (2), 85-88.
3. Сабирова, Н. Э. (2018). ОСОБЕННОСТИ СИМВОЛОВ ОБРЯДОВЫХ ПЕСЕН, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ДРЕВНИМИ КУЛЬТАМИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND EDUCATION* (pp. 73-74).
4. Otajonova, M. (2020). The semantic functions of myth in an artistic context. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*, 9(11), 225-229.
5. Omanbaevna, O. M. (2020). MYTHS AND MODERN UZBEK STORIES (some commentary on the story of Nazar Eshankul's "The tune of a flute" myth-story). *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 8(12), 49-53.
6. Атажанова, М. А. (2021). МИФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АРХЕТИПЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ УЗБЕКСКОЙ ПРОЗЕ И ИХ ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПРИРОДА. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 143-148.
7. XOLMONOVA, Z. (2015). BABÜRNÂMEDEKİ BAZIKELİMELERİN TARİH? VE ETİMOLOJİK TAHLİLİ. *Journal of Social Sciences/Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi* (2146-4561), 5(9).
8. Otajanova, M. (2021). A UNIQUE ARTISTIC INTERPRETATION OF THE ETHNOCULTURAL VALUES OF THE TURKIC PEOPLES. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(06), 108-115.

9. Otajanova, M. (2022). ANALYSIS OF MYTHOLOGYSMS IN MODERN UZBEK PROSE. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, 11(5), 16-27.

10. Сабирова, Н. Э. (2019). ВАЖНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УЧАЩИМИСЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМОВ УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА С ЦВЕТОВЫМИ КОМПОНЕНТАМИ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ. In EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY (pp. 34-36).

11. Otajanova, M. (2022). Mythologism in modern Uzbek prose. Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 6, 56-65.

12. ALAVUTDINOVA GANIEVNA, N. (2015). PLACE OF PROFESSOR AYYUB GULOMOV IN FORMING OF MORPHOLOGICAL VIEWPOINTS IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS OF XX CENTURY. Electronic Turkish Studies, 10(12).

13. Otajanova, M. (2022). Mythopoetic interpretation in the artistic work. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 12(7), 98-108.

